

Scope & Topics

International Journal of Ubiquitous Computing (IJU) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal provides excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of ubiquitous computing. Current information age is witnessing a dramatic use of digital and electronic devices in the workplace and beyond. Ubiquitous Computing presents a rather arduous requirement of robustness, reliability and availability to the end user. Ubiquitous computing has received a significant and sustained research interest in terms of designing and deploying large scale and high performance computational applications in real life. The aim of the journal is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Topic of Interest

- Architectural Structure, Design Decisions and Philosophies
- Autonomic Management of Ubiquitous Systems
- Context and Location Awareness, Context Based and Implicit Computing
- Distributed Computing
- Ubicomp Human-Computer Interaction for Devices
- Intelligent Devices and Environments
- Internet Computing and Applications
- Interoperability and Large Scale Deployment
- Middleware Services and Agent Technologies
- Personalized & special field applications
- Security Issues and Applications
- Service Discovery Mechanisms and Protocols
- Software Infrastructures
- System Support Infrastructures and Services
- Ubiquitous systems and trust
- User Interfaces and Interaction Models
- Virtualization Over Networks of Devices
- Wearable Computers and Technologies
- Wireless Networking and Mobile, Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing
- Wireless/Mobile Service Management and Delivery
- Mobile Computing
- Network Protocols & Wireless Communication
- Internet of Things
- IoT-Big Data

Paper Submission:

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: iju@airconline.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates:

- **Submission Deadline : June 04, 2022**
- Notification : July 04, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : July 12, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: iju@airconline.com

Paper Submission: <http://coneco2009.com/submissions/imagination/home.html>